

Title	Authors	Year	Publication type	Type of architecture evaluation.	Quality Attributes	Attribute Number to Evaluate	References (property systems, quality attributes, quality models)	Validation type
A fuzzy evaluation method for system of systems meta-architecture	Louis Pape, Kristin Giammarco, John Colombi, Cihan Dagli, Nil Kilicay-Ergin	2013	Conference	Quantitative	performance, affordability, flexibility, robustness	Multi-attribute	None	Illustration
A service-oriented modeling and simulation framework for rapid development of distributed applications	W.T. Tsai a, Chun Fan a, Yinong Chen a, *, Ray Paul b	2005	Journal	Quantitative	Dependability, performance	Multi-attribute	None	Experiment
An Analytic Workbench Perspective to Evolution of System of System Architecture	Navindran Davendralingam, Daniel DeLaurentis, Zhemei Fang, Cesare Guariniello, Seung Yeobhan, Karen Marais, Ankur Mour, Payuna Uday.	2014	Conference	Quantitative	Operability, resilience, interdependency, performance y reliability	Multi-attribute	None	Illustration
Assessing Robustness in Systems of Systems Meta-architectures	Louis Pape, Cihan Dagli	2014	Conference	Quantitative	Robustness	One-attribute	None	Experiment
Genetic Algorithm Optimization of SoS Meta-Architecture Attributes for Fuzzy Rule Based Assessment	Andrew Renault*, Cihan Dagli	2016	Conference	Quantitative	Reliability, Survivability, modularity, adaptability, controllability, portability, flexibility, maintainability, affordability, transportability.	Multi-attribute	Key Performance Attributes	Illustration
Integrated Analysis of Functional and Developmental Interdependencies to Quantify and Trade-offilities for System-of-Systems Design, Architecture, and Evolution	Cesare Guariniello, Daniel DeLaurentis	2014	Conference	Quantitative	Resilience, flexibility, robustness	Multi-attribute	None	Illustration
Scaling up software architecture analysis	Rick Kazman,b, *, Michael Gagliardib, William Woodb	2011	Journal	Hybrid	availability, modifiability, performance, security, testability, and usability	Multi-attribute	Tactics BCK	None

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An Illities-Driven Methodology for the Analysis of Gaps of Stakeholders Needs in Space Systems Conceptual Design	Sabrina Corpino, Fabio Nichele	2016	Journal	Hybrid	QoS, Usability, Flexibility, Interoperability, Sustainability	Multi-attribute	Life-Cycle Properties of Engineering Systems	Case study
FRAMEWORK FOR MANAGING SYSTEM-OF-SYSTEMS ILITIES	KANG Shian Chin, PEE Eng Yau, SIM Kok Wah, PANG Chung Kiang	2016	Journal	Hybrid	Robustness, Evolvability	Multi-attribute	Life-Cycle Properties of Engineering Systems	None
Towards Modelling and Analysing Non-functional Properties of Systems of Systems	Vanea Chiprianov, Katrina Falkner, Laurent Gallon, Manuel Munier	2014	Conference	Quantitative	Security and performance	Multi-attribute	None	None
A Model-Driven Approach for Evaluating System of Systems	Xiaokai Xia, Ji Wu, Chao Liu	2013	Conference	Hybrid	Performance and effectiveness	Multi-attribute	None	Case study
Evaluation method of system-of-systems architecture using knowledge-based executable model	Xiong Jian, Ge Bing-feng, Zhang Xiao-ke	2010	Conference	Quantitative	Performance	One-attribute	Measure of Performance	Case study
System of Systems Architecture Generation and Evaluation using Evolutionary Algorithms	Joseph J. Simpson, Cihan H. Dagli	2008	Conference	Quantitative	Flexibility, survivability, robustness, reliability, availability, affordability	Multi-attribute	Measures of Effectiveness	Illustration
Architecture-Based Interoperability Evaluation in Evolutions of Networked Enterprises	Pin Chen	2005	Workshop	Hybrid	Interoperability	One-attribute	None	Illustration
Evaluation of IT Systems Considering Characteristics as System of Systems	Daichi Kimura*, Takao Osaki, Kazuo Yanoo, Sayaka Izukura, Hiroshi Sakaki, Atsushi Kobayashi	2011	Conference	Quantitative	Performance and reliability	Multi-attribute	None	Case study

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An Approach to Facilitate Decision Making on Architecture Evolution Strategies	Zhemei Fang, Daniel DeLaurentisa, Navindran Davendralingama	2013	Conference	Quantitative	Performance	One-attribute	None	Case study
Development Interdependency Modeling for System-of-Systems (SoS) using Bayesian Networks: SoS Management Strategy Planning	Seung Yeob Han and Daniel DeLaurentis	2013	Conference	Quantitative	Performance	One-attribute	None	Illustration
Dependency Analysis of System-of-Systems Operational and Development Networks	Cesare Guariniello*, Daniel DeLaurentisa	2013	Conference	Quantitative	Reliability, operability, resilience	Multi-attribute	None	Illustration
Flexible and Intelligent Learning Architectures for SoS (FILA-SoS): Architectural Evolution in Systems-of-Systems	Siddhartha Agarwal*, Louis E. Papea, Cihan H. Daglia*, Nil K. Erginb, David Enkea, Abhijit Gosavia, Ruwen Qina, Dincer Konura, Renzhong Wangc, Ram Deepak Gottapua	2015	Conference	Quantitative	Performance, Robustness, Affordability, Flexibility	Multi-attribute	Key Performance Attributes	Illustration
System of systems architecture feasibility analysis to support tradespace exploration	Stephen E. Gillespie, Ronald E. Giachetti, Alejandro Hernandez	2017	Conference	Quantitative	Feasibility	One-attribute	None	Case study
Evaluating System of Systems Resilience using Interdependency Analysis	Seung Yeob Han, Karen Marais, and Daniel DeLaurentis	2012	Conference	Quantitative	Resilience	One-attribute	None	Case study

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An Architecture-based Approach to Identifying System-of Systems Alternatives	Kelly Griendling, Dimitri Mavris	2010	Conference	Hybrid	Feasibility	One-attribute	None	Illustration
Multi-objective Stochastic Heuristic Methodology for Tradespace Exploration of a Network Centric System of Systems	Atmika Singh, Cihan H. Dagli	2009	Conference	Quantitative	Performance	One-attribute	None	Illustration
A Uniform Approach for System of Systems Architecture Evaluation	Michael Gagliardi, William G. Wood, John Klein, and John Morley	2009	Conference	Hybrid	availability, modifiability, performance, security, testability, and usability	Multi-attribute	Tactics BCK	None